

PEDAGOGICAL MECHANISMS OF DEVELOPING CREATIVE COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TEACHERS BASED ON MODERN APPROACHES

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Abstract. *Today, in the establishment of pedagogical mechanisms for the development of creative competence of future teachers based on modern approaches, one of the important issues is the continuous broadening of the knowledge, skills and abilities of students in the mastering of didactic systematic lessons given to students in practical and production training, and the improvement of creativity skills. The article pays attention to this issue, the results of work efficiency are justified.*

Keywords: *teachers, creativity, competence, modern education, approach, development, pedagogical mechanism, quality education, efficiency, professional skills, creative competence and creative approach, goal, pedagogical control, creative competence.*

The introduction of the article talks about the pedagogical mechanisms of developing the creative competence of future teachers based on modern approaches, in which the teacher takes the leading place in the organization of today's educational process and its effectiveness. Their work and activities in preparing young people to work productively in various fields of agriculture, in learning various professions, are incomparable. Because school teachers are responsible for organizing and conducting vocational training.

Due to this, in the course of extracurricular and extracurricular activities and activities of the educational system, mastering the didactic systematic lessons given to students and continuously widening and deepening the knowledge, skills and abilities of students in practical and production classes, determining the scope and pace of improving creativity skills are considered important issues in the educational system.

It is self-evident that the task before the teachers is to make them, on the basis of their didactic education, to form professional knowledge, skills and abilities at a high level, to improve their professional skills, creative competence, to share it with the demands of the growing pedagogical process, in turn, to control their pedagogical activities. plans to make appropriate adjustments to this creative activity based on its results, if necessary. In this, the scope and quality of school education teachers' knowledge, skills and qualifications, the quality and effectiveness of the organization and delivery of education, professional skills, creative competence and creative approach, and the creative competence of pedagogical control are achieved. At the same time, the scientific basis and systematic structure that determine the qualities of creativity potential are considered.

Like any other quality (virtue), creativity is not formed suddenly. Creativity is consistently formed and developed at certain stages. So, when do the characteristics of creativity appear in a person's work?

Figure 1. A systematic model of creativity qualities.

Although creativity is often visible in children's activities, this situation does not guarantee that children will achieve creative achievements in the future. It only represents the possibility that they need to master this or that creative skill.

Clubs, Olympiads, extracurricular activities organized by the teacher and the school administration allow them to have a creative approach.

When developing creativity in children, it is necessary to pay attention to the following factors:

- 1) encouraging children's independence and strengthening their responsibility;
- 2) creating an opportunity for children to organize independent activities;
- 3) it was considered necessary to pay attention to children's interests.

In the future, serious work is being done on a nationwide scale to create the didactic conditions of the pedagogical control process, based on the optimal selection of its appropriate forms, types, methods and tools, to develop the methodology of creative competence for its effective implementation, and to enrich its content. Among them, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4884 dated November 6, 2020 "On additional measures to further improve the education system" and the "State nationwide program for the development of school education in 2004-2009" adopted in 2004 and 2006. It is possible to include the "Regulations on organization and transfer of teacher personnel attestation" approved on January 18.

In addition, in the analysis, study and evaluation of the level of professional skills, activities and creative skills of specialists in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the practical work of the leading specialists of the Attestation and Accreditation Center under the State Test Center under the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, this field as a state order it is worth noting that it provides direct support to its development.

The following aspects can be found necessary in monitoring the pedagogical skills, activity and creativity of future teachers:

A) to determine whether educational work is focused on a specific goal, scientifically based, and its content is correctly selected;

B) to determine the quality of the results of learning professional skills and creativity skills, to determine the stages of development, the level of development, and to illuminate future directions;

C) It is necessary to pay attention to identifying tasks such as the development of alternative and effective methods of education and upbringing of future teachers, the formation of the world view of students and teachers, and the establishment of relationships based on mutual trust, friendship, and cooperation among all members of the pedagogical team.

Due to the lack of opportunity to tell future teachers about all the details of applying a systematic approach to the process of controlling the pedagogical activity and creative competence, we will make it easier for the examinees and auditors to control the creative activity and the creative competence, and in order to implement it correctly and truthfully, some of its we limit ourselves to the description of one important feature. This is expressed through several systems to control the creative competence of future teachers in their pedagogical activities:

- orderly, because it is planned in advance, there are clear locations of control elements;
- it has speed, it is constantly developing, improving and changing;
- has two opposite sides - controller and controlled;
- linearity – orientation towards a specific goal;
- recoverable - a specific control process can be repeated at any time;
- complex - mainly consists of six parts;
- centered - the vector lines of all parts meet in the part called "Inspected";
- multi-level - a system consisting of control beginning, climax, conclusion;
- secondary – the formed pedagogical control system, which has a clear character and allows to add new parts that need to be checked and evaluated;
- immanent - the pedagogical control system can communicate with parts of other systems as long as it is in integral relationship with its constituent parts;
- it remains unchanged even when changes are aimed at the structure of the static pedagogical control system;
- heterogeneous – the pedagogical control system defines a creative competence consisting of parts with different characteristics.

Teacher's creativity skills. The teacher's creativity is reflected in his creative approach to the organization of professional activities organized by him. In recent years, this situation is represented by the concept of "Pedagogical creativity".

Pedagogical creativity is manifested in the ability of a pedagogue to create new ideas that serve to ensure the effectiveness of the educational process, as well as to positively solve existing pedagogical problems, unlike traditional pedagogical thinking.

The teacher's creativity is reflected as his general characteristic. It is the first condition and result of creative activity. This quality represents a person's ability and willingness to express themselves. In addition, on the basis of creative competence, the personal abilities, natural and social strength of each specialist are manifested as a whole.

Creative competence is closely related to creativity focused on the cognitive process. The creative competence of the teacher, in contrast to traditional thinking, is manifested in: quickness and flexibility of thinking;

ability to create new ideas; not thinking in one way;
originality; initiative; tolerance of uncertainty;
to be intelligent.

In order for the teacher to have creativity skills, he should pay attention to the following in his professional activities:

creative approach to professional activity;
active in creating new ideas;
independent study of advanced pedagogical achievements and experiences;
sharing ideas with colleagues about pedagogical achievements.

The self-development and self-expression of each pedagogue is directly related to his creativity.

The future teacher should be aware of the uniqueness of the subject he teaches, the practice and production of teachers in the educational process, the teacher should not only analyze various pedagogical situations, but also solve problems related to the production of products directly from it, as well as the production process in a continuous, uniform manner. A lot of machinery, equipment, etc. an unpleasant situation that may occur unexpectedly while working with (students' knowledge and skills of new techniques and technologies are shallow, they are not adapted to work in new conditions, or some production operations are repeated in the same (monotonous) way and attention is lost due to distractions, falling asleep, confusion, loss of self, injury as a result of fear) is also manifested in a direct connection with the demand to solve problems in a timely and short period of time.

At the time when the integration of the industry and agriculture of our independent republic with the world economy is expanding and deepening, it is necessary to accustom students to work in the conditions of market relations from the first stages of the education system.

In monitoring the future teacher's pedagogical skills, activities, and creativity, the following aspects should be considered:

- a) to determine whether the educational work is focused on a specific goal, scientifically based, and its content is correctly selected;
- b) determining the quality of the results of labor and professional activity, determining the stages of development, the level of development, and clarifying future directions;
- c) it is necessary to pay attention to the development of alternative effective methods of education and training, the formation of the worldviews of students and teachers, the establishment of relationships based on mutual trust, friendship, and cooperation among all members of the pedagogical team, and the determination of such tasks as the pursuit of a single goal.

In addition to the fact that the processes of controlling the complex pedagogical activity of a future teacher, determining the level of his professional skills, defining service categories and recommending him to various titles have not been objectively resolved, one-sidedness, and in some cases, gross shortcomings and mistakes are allowed in the implementation of this process. Taking into account the uniqueness of his pedagogical activity, it is appropriate to study and analyze the aspects of his professional activity from all sides, as well as to give specific scientific, practical conclusions and recommendations about the results of his activity, in order to control him in multidisciplinary directions and to truly assess the level of professional skill. It is self-evident that, in accordance with the progress achieved in the scientific-technical, socio-economic

development, the improvement of the pedagogical activity in the existing methods in the developing educational system will not fail to give the expected result.

In conclusion, it can be said that today's future teachers actively participate in educational work, they are required to organize their activities in sync with the times, and the pedagogical mechanisms of developing the creative competence of future teachers based on modern approaches are the source of creating new creative opportunities every day. Today's teacher, in the organization of training sessions, abandons the previously planned types of training, forming and developing critical and creative thinking of students, forcing them to think creatively, i.e. to come up with ideas, changing the attitude to education, encouraging them to achieve success. must be a factor.

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